

Disruptive electrical propulsion - power processing unit

Horizon Europe project DEEP PPU

RF Harness Modelling

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To accurately characterize the high frequency harmonics that appear due to the harness parasitics, a harness model based on real measurements has been used.

A harness can be modeled as a network of resistors, inductors and capacitors:

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The harness consists of a positive cable and a negative cable, hence the overall behavior can be modeled as a two-port network. To model the total effect of the network impedances, we will use the impedance matrix.

$$\begin{pmatrix} V_1 \\ V_2 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} Z_{11} & Z_{12} \\ Z_{21} & Z_{22} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} I_1 \\ I_2 \end{pmatrix}$$

Since the harness has the same behavior in both directions $Z_{11} = Z_{22}$ and $Z_{12} = Z_{21}$, only two values have to be calculated. To obtain these values, two measurements on the harness are performed: one with the opposite end in open-circuit and one with the opposite end in short-circuit.

$$Z_{11} = Z_{open}$$

$$Z_{12} = \sqrt{Z_{11}(Z_{11} - Z_{short})}$$

Introducing the model into LTspice

To be able to simulate the harness model, a T-model based on the calculated impedance matrix was introduced in LTspice:

Two port network T-model based on the impedance matrix parameters.

Since the T-model impedances are based on the real measurement data values, they match the real harness measurements closely. This model has been really useful to design the filter that dampens the high frequency harmonics caused by the parasitic capacitance of the harness.

Open impedance real measurement (left) and LTspice model comparison (right)

Short impedance real measurement (left) and LTspice model comparison (right)

About project

The DEEP-PPU consortium will develop a disruptive Power Processing Unit for medium and high-power GIT. The project is a natural continuation of GIESEPP-MP, where a first step has been taken to develop a power supply for the screen grid and integrate it within the current PPU design for ArianeGroup RIT-2X thruster. The activity is focused on the improvement and optimization of the power electronics as one of the major cost drivers of an electric propulsion system, in particular for gridded ion technology.

Project consortium

DEEP-PPU team is composed of 6 organisations. Each of the partners is responsible for a specific work package or task within the project. Most of the partners have worked together before. Project coordinator - Airbus Crisa.

Airbus Crisa

Airbus Crisa
Project coordinator & PPU
www.crisa.es

AIRBUS

Airbus DS
Responsible for / definition of space specific requirements
www.airbus.com

Polytechnic University of Madrid Centro de Electrónica Industrial
Responsible for Radiofrequency Generator electronics
www.cei.upm.es

AXON CABLE
Responsible for interconnection of systems / Manufacturer for space harness assemblies
www.axon-cable.com

WIT Berry
Responsible for communication and dissemination activities
www.witberry.eu

Fraza
Responsible for expertise in magnetics design
www.fraza.si

Competitive advantages proposed by DEEP-PPU

DEEP PPU team's proposed solutions stands out with significant mass and cost reduction compared to the existing solutions on the market. It aims to strengthen the EU's space sector competitiveness in the international market and secure the autonomy of supply for critical technologies and equipment.

50%
Cost reduction

30%
Mass and volume reduction

The integration of the RFG unit within the PPU

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